

**"Application of Cost Accounting Standards
in Manufacturing Industries and
Challenges"**

A Report

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements
for Award of

**POST DOCTORAL RESEARCH
CERTIFICATE FELLOW**

by

DR. KUNAL SIL

Roll No: 19SUPDRCOI

Under the supervision of

Dr. P. S. Aithal

**DEPARTMENT OF COMMERCE AND MANAGEMENT
SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF COMMERCE AND MANAGEMENT
MUKKA, KARNATAKA, INDIA**

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Declaration

I hereby declare that except where specific reference is made to the work of others, the contents of this Report is original and have not been submitted in whole or in part for consideration for any other degree or qualification in this, or any other university. This Report is my own work and does not contain any outcome of work done in collaboration with others, except as specified in the text and Acknowledgements.

Signature :

Name : Dr. Kunal Sil

Roll No : 19SUPDRCOI

Place: MUKKA

Date:

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

Srinivas Nagar, – 574 146, Mangalore, Phone :0824-2477456

(Private University Established by Karnataka Govt. ACT No.42 of 2013.

Web:www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in, Email: info@srinivasuniversity.edu.in

Certificate

This is to certify that entitled “**Application of Cost Accounting Standards in Manufacturing Industries and Challenges**” submitted by **DR. KUNAL SIL** to **SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY** for the award of the Post Doctoral Research Certificate Fellow is a Bonafede record of the research work carried out by him under my supervision and guidance. The content of the Report, in full or parts have not been submitted to any other institute or university for the award of any degree or diploma.

Supervisor: Dr. P.S. Aithal

Professor:

Place : Mukka

Date : ___/___/_____

Application of Cost Accounting Standards in Manufacturing Industries and Challenges

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DR. KUNAL SIL

Synopsis

Cost Accounting Standard 22 is applied in Manufacturing Industries for determining Manufacturing cost. This standard basically deals with manufacturing cost of excisable goods. This also lays out methods of classification, measurement and assignment for determination of the Manufacturing Cost of excisable goods and the presentation and disclosure in cost statements (CAS-22).

This standard works upon the principles and techniques of shaping the Research, and Development Costs and their categorization, dimension and assignment for calculating of the cost of product or service, and the presentation and revelation in cost statements.

The primary objective of setting this standard is to bring consistency and reliability in the values and methods of formulating the Research, and Development Costs with reasonable accuracy and presentation of the same.

Development is the use of research findings or any other knowledge to a plan or any plan for the production of new or considerably improved materials, devices, products, processes, systems or services prior to the commencement of commercial production or use.

Empirical findings have found that majority of cost accounting standards feature characteristics exercise a significant influence of application of indirect cost in allocation and absorption in product manufacturing. System's inability to disaggregate costs according their behavior is not done in a scientific manner.

The innovation of this study rests on the development of a cohesive framework for the use of CAS 22 facilitating indirect cost calculation.

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Chapter I- Introduction

IFAC's mission statement gives due emphasis to the public interest and recognizes that a fundamental way to protect this public interest is to develop, promote, and enforce internationally recognized standards as a means of ensuring the credibility of information upon which investors and other stakeholders depend.

IFAC, therefore, strives to serve the public interest through the facilitation of the development of standards in auditing, education, ethics, and public sector financial reporting by:

- advocating for transparency and convergence in financial reporting; and
- implementing a membership compliance program.

IFAC also provides International Good Practice Guidance for professional accountants in business.

In line with this framework, and even prior to the foundation of IFAC, professional and regulatory bodies all over the world develop accounting standards based on generally accepted principles and practices followed in their countries. These have been enforced through law, promoted by a regulatory mechanism, or voluntarily followed by all business entities. Standards help to ensure uniformity and consistency in the preparation and reporting of various financial statements.

Post-World War II, all economies, irrespective of their economic structure, started to lay much greater emphasis on cost accounting principles and ensured that all business organizations follow them, at the very least when dealing with the state. Cost accounting was developed as a separate discipline in accountancy, and promoted efficiency in resource utilization. Gradually, new skills developed in this field and it slowly attained a prime position in any organization's functioning.

IFAC's International Good Practice Guidance, *Evaluating and Improving Costing in Organizations*, highlights the importance of cost accounting to organizations.

Value Creation: This value-creation schematic highlights all the key elements of how IFAC creates and protects value and is based on the IFAC Strategic Plan for 2021 and beyond. This diagram is comprehensive, covering all parts of IFAC's ecosystem, and helps IFAC communicate internally and externally and explain our ecosystem.

Review: IFAC's annual review is a significant element of accountability to member organizations, the Forum of Firms, and other key stakeholders. It provides an overview of IFAC, including governance and stakeholder engagement, strategic objectives, value creation process, and performance highlights.

2020 was an exceptionally difficult year by any standard. And yet, all around the world, people rose to the occasion in ways big and small to meet the challenges brought about by COVID-19. The accountancy profession responded quickly to support our public interest mandate, and the people, communities, businesses, and economies we serve. IFAC is proud to say we did the same.

2019 IFAC Integrated Annual Review: For IFAC and the accountancy profession, 2019 was full of accomplishments. We sharpened our voice, focused on the issues, and supported our member organizations in new and innovative ways. We developed clear, concise, and bold Points of View on pressing issues for the profession, continued the conversation on how to help professional accountants and member organizations prepare for the future, and fulfilled our commitment to support global standard setting in the public interest.

The COVID-19 pandemic has not interrupted our progress, but added greater urgency to many of the issues we've been tackling and presented both new challenges and opportunities. Time will not stop for the world to recover. The full impact of the pandemic might not be known for years, but measuring, analyzing, and reporting to support good decision making will be the difference between a strong recovery and a weak recovery. Now more than ever, the role of the accountancy profession is clear and indispensable, and so is our commitment to the public interest.

We look forward to continued partnerships with our member organizations, the Forum of Firms, and other key stakeholders, as we launch the accountancy profession into a new decade.

Statement of Accounting Policies For the year ended December 31, 2020:

Basis of Preparation: The International Federation of Accountants' (IFAC) financial statements have been prepared in accordance with International Public Sector Accounting Standards (IPSAS) issued by the International Public Sector Accounting Standards Board. Where an IPSAS does not address a particular issue, the appropriate International Financial Reporting Standard (IFRS) issued by the International Accounting Standards Board (IASB) is applied. The financial statements have been prepared on the historical cost basis unless otherwise stated in the accounting policies. The financial statements are presented in United States dollars, the functional and reporting currency of IFAC. Estimates and Assumptions The preparation of financial statements in accordance with IPSAS requires the use of estimates and assumptions that affect the reported amounts of assets and liabilities at the date of the financial statements and the reported amounts of revenue and expenses during the reporting period.

The most significant estimates and assumptions relate to the measurement of the defined benefit pension plan expense and withdrawal liability, and the allocation of revenues, expenses, assets, and liabilities for the purposes of segment reporting (Note 19). Although these estimates are based on management's best knowledge of current events and actions, actual results ultimately may significantly differ from those estimates. Significant Accounting Policies A. Accounting Standards Update New IPSAS standards issued during 2020 have been considered and are not expected to have a material impact on IFAC's financial statements. B. Revenue Recognition Revenue is recognized when it is probable that the economic benefits associated with the transaction will flow to the organization and the amount of the revenue can be measured reliably. Membership dues Revenue from annual membership dues is initially recorded as deferred revenue and recognized on a straight-line basis over the reporting period. Membership dues are reported net of any approved discounts. Forum of Firms revenue Revenue from the Forum of Firms (Forum) is invoiced quarterly and recognized on a straight-line basis over the reporting period. Revenue from the Forum consists of a contribution (dues) of an agreed amount on an annual basis, and reimbursement of an amount equal to the expenses incurred by the Transnational Auditors Committee during the reporting period.

IFAC 2020 Financial Statements: Other sources of funding IFAC receive other sources of funding from governments, donor agencies, and other institutions, as well as from alliances and other organizations. Other sources of funding are generally in the form of restricted and unrestricted grants, contributions, and expense reimbursements. Revenue from other sources of funding is recognized when IFAC has complied with all the stipulations or conditions (as defined in IPSAS 23, Revenue from Non-Exchange Transactions – Taxes and Transfers) implicit in the underlying agreements, and there is reasonable assurance that the funding will be received. Other sources of funding are recognized in the statement of financial performance on a systematic basis over the periods in which IFAC recognizes as expenses the related costs for which the funding is intended to compensate. Other sources of funding for compensation of expenses or losses already incurred or for giving immediate financial support to IFAC with no future related costs is recognized in the statement of financial performance when it becomes receivable.

Publications revenue: Revenue from publications is recognized when the publications are shipped or downloaded from the IFAC website. Interest income Interest income from a financial asset is recognized when it is probable that the economic benefit will flow to IFAC and the amount can be reasonably measured. Services in-kind A variety of board and committee services are provided by highly qualified volunteers. IFAC does not recognize these services in the financial statements as their value cannot be reliably measured. C. Employee Entitlements Employee entitlements to salaries, wages, paid time off, retirement benefits, and other benefits are recognized when they are earned.

Annual paid time off is calculated on an actual entitlement basis at current rates of pay. IFAC provides retirement benefits for employees under defined contribution plans and a defined benefit plan. Payments to the defined contribution plans are recognized as expenses as they become due. IFAC is one of three sponsoring employers that participate in the multiple employer defined benefit pension plan (Plan) of the American Institute of Certified Public Accountants (AICPA). During the year ended December 31, 2020, IFAC withdrew from the Plan (Note 11). The Plan is partly funded. The liability or asset recognized in the statement of financial position in respect of the Plan is the present value of the defined benefit obligation at the end of the reporting period less the fair value of plan assets. The defined benefit obligation is calculated annually by independent actuaries using the projected unit credit method. The present value of the defined benefit obligation is determined by discounting the estimated future cash outflows using interest rates of high-quality corporate bonds, and that have terms approximating to the terms of the related obligation. The net interest cost is calculated by applying the discount rate to the net

IFAC 2020 Financial Statements: Balance of the defined benefit obligation and the fair value of plan assets. This cost is included in employee costs in the statement of financial performance. Re-measurement of gains and losses arising from experience adjustments and changes in actuarial assumptions are recognized in the period in which they occur, directly to accumulated surpluses in the statements of net assets/equity. Changes in the present value of the defined benefit obligation resulting from plan amendments or curtailments are recognized in the statement of financial performance as past service costs. There were no plan amendments or curtailments in 2020 or 2019. D. Property and Equipment Property and equipment are carried at cost and are depreciated / amortized on a straight-line basis over their expected useful lives. The useful lives, residual values, and depreciation methods are reviewed annually.

Refer to (F) Impairment below. The estimated useful lives of property and equipment are as follows: Office equipment 3 to 5 years Furniture and fittings 5 to 7 years Leasehold alterations Shorter of the life of the lease or useful life Gains and losses on disposals are determined by comparing proceeds with carrying amounts and are included in the statement of financial performance. Repairs and maintenance are charged to the statement of financial performance during the period in which they are incurred. E. Intangible Assets Intangible assets consist of software licenses and website development costs. An intangible asset is recognized when it is identifiable, the organization has control over the asset, it is probable that economic benefits will flow to the organization, and the cost of the asset can be measured reliably. Intangible assets that do not meet these criteria are recognized as an expense in the period in which the expense is incurred. Intangible assets are carried at cost and are amortized on a straight-line basis over the estimated useful lives of the assets, generally 3 to 5 years. Refer to (F) Impairment below.

Impairment IFAC reviews the carrying amounts of its property and equipment and intangible assets if there is indication that impairment exists. If any such indication exists, the recoverable amount of the asset is estimated in order to determine the extent of the impairment loss, if any. If the recoverable amount of an asset is estimated to be less than the carrying amount, the carrying amount is reduced to the recoverable amount. Impairment losses are recognized as an expense in the statement of financial performance in the period the impairment is incurred.

Financial Instruments: Financial instruments include cash and cash equivalents, accounts receivable, and accounts payable. Financial instruments are recognized in the statement of financial position at cost, which approximates fair value due to their short-term nature. Cash and cash equivalents include cash on hand and on deposit at banks, and other short-term liquid investments with original maturities of three months or less. Membership dues and other receivables are carried at original invoice amount less any subsequently approved discount, and less an estimate made for doubtful receivables based on reviews of all outstanding amounts at year-end. Bad debts are provided for when identified.

Operating Leases: Leases are classified as operating leases when a significant portion of the risks and rewards of ownership are retained by the lessor. Lease agreements may contain provisions for future rent increases, rent-free periods, or other lease incentives. The total amount of rent due over the lease term, reduced for any lease incentives, is recognized in rent expense on a straight-line basis over the term of the respective lease. The difference between rent expense and the amount paid is recognized in deferred rent in the accompanying statement of financial position.

Taxation: IFAC has received an exemption from the US Internal Revenue Service (IRS) from federal income taxes under Section 501(a), as an entity described in Section 501(c)(6) of the Internal Revenue Code of 1986 (IRC), as amended. IFAC is required to make the appropriate tax payments on any income considered unrelated to its exempt purpose. IFAC also is exempt from Swiss income taxes (Note 1).

Foreign Currencies Transactions in foreign currencies are translated to United States dollars at the rates of exchange prevailing at the date of the transactions. Assets and liabilities denominated in foreign currencies are translated at the rates of exchange prevailing at the reporting date. The resulting gains or losses are recognized in the statement of financial performance.

Criticalities of Standard Costing: Standard costs are “would-be” or “expected” costs; what it *should* cost to make a product. They are management’s best, most precise estimate of how much material, labor and manufacturing overhead dollars are required to produce a single product. Manufacturers develop and assign these estimates for a product, then measure them against the actual costs to produce a product.

For example, if our standard cost per unit is \$100, your costs may break down as follows:

- a) \$60 material (e.g., cardboard, plastic, steel, etc.)
- b) 20 labor (includes people who regularly touch the product during production)
- c) \$20 overhead (includes shipping, receiving, plant maintenance, plant management, etc.)

In manufacturing, business leaders generally understand the notion of standard costing from a definitional standpoint. **The confusion is around how it is applied, measured or benchmarked in financial statements.** For example: what do the numbers mean in practical terms for your business? If there is profit erosion, how do you connect costing data from the financial reports back onto the shop floor? Where do you look to make improvements?

A lot of uncertainties have been found around which components comprise a product's standard costs. Common mistakes include factoring into the product cost your *sales staff* or your *direct delivery cost to customers*. While this data is valuable for other analytics, it should not be included as a standard costing input.

Rather than assigning actual costs of direct material, direct labor and manufacturing overhead to a product, which can be costly and time consuming, **manufacturers can use standard costing to reveal variances between the expected and actual costs.** These variances are measured in the income statement, where management will review and analyze material, labor and overhead deviations from the standards.

Understanding the root causes of these differences can go a long way in driving process and other shop floor improvements. In turn, driving gross profit improvements. Standard costing also aggregates data to simplify reporting. This of course requires a system that can capture many different process details and transfer them to the financial reporting system.

ERP System: Many issues with standard costing data are often the result of *how your financial systems are configured*. Your manufacturing ERP system should be set up to gather and data mine much of the critical details comprising your costing data (as defined by your costing standards) so that managers can view and develop key metrics to drive continuous improvement. And even within sophisticated systems, these metrics must be tied to your financial/accounting system to be valuable. **If our financial system is not configured properly, critical details will get filtered out in the transfer** – and that presents huge problems when trying to perform timely and effective root-cause analysis.

Root Cause Analysis: The simplest way of understanding manufacturing variances for each component (e.g., material, labor and manufacturing overhead) is to evaluate the differences between standard and actual as a price and/or usage variance. Then, the most critical step is digging into the *reasons* behind those variances to understand how to translate those results into actionable information that drives continuous improvements on the shop floor. For example:

- a) Why was there excess material usage?
- b) Was the variance the result of inefficiencies from breakdown in machinery or equipment?
- c) And why did this occur?
- d) Is this because we're not adequately tracking and completing scheduled maintenance on machinery and equipment at the right intervals thereby minimizing unplanned downtime?
- e) Our root-cause analysis usually holds the answers to these questions. Timing is vital here, too. The sooner the manufacturing and accounting system reports a variance, the sooner management can direct its efforts to resolving the root problem.

Mass Production: Another very important concept is *absorption*. In simple terms, *absorption* is the continuous measuring of whether actual material, labor and overhead spend is close to your standard costs estimated to produce your product for that same period.

For example, let's say our *actual dollars* spent for materials, labor, and overhead is \$1.3 million. Your *standard cost* to produce your finished product for the same period is \$1.0 million. This means your standards are not adequately reflecting, or *absorbing*, the actual costs to produce.

So, what does this all mean? **If our standard costs are too low (as in this example), it would have an adverse impact on gross profit.** This is because your pricing decisions are based on what you currently *think* it costs you to produce. Here again, your root-cause analysis will hold the answer. It will reveal a variety of factors (i.e., you have an actual volume that is lower than budgeted, material costs that are higher than expected, more overhead spend or machine hours than budgeted, etc.) that will help you respond in a timely fashion and inform what your next steps should be.

Chapter 2- Cost Accounting Standard (CAS22)

The following is the COST ACCOUNTING STANDARD – 22 (CAS - 22) issued by the Council of The Institute of Cost Accountants of India for determination of “MANUFACTURING COST”.

In this Standard, the standard portions have been set in bold italic type. This standard should be read in the context of the background material which has been set in normal type.

1. Introduction

1.1 This standard deals with the principles and methods of determining the Manufacturing Cost of excisable goods.

1.2 This standard deals with the principles and methods of classification, measurement and assignment for determination of the Manufacturing Cost of excisable goods and the presentation and disclosure in cost statements.

2. Objective- The objective of this standard is to bring uniformity and consistency in the principles and methods of determining the Manufacturing Cost of excisable goods.

3. Scope This standard should be applied to cost statements which require classification, measurement, assignment, presentation and disclosure of Manufacturing Cost of excisable goods.

4. Definitions- The following terms are being used in this standard with the meaning specified.

4.1 Abnormal and non-recurring cost: An unusual or atypical cost whose occurrence is usually irregular and unexpected and/or due to some abnormal situation of the production or operation.

4.2 Administrative Overheads: Cost of all activities relating to general management and administration of an organization. Administrative overheads need to be analysed in relation to production/manufacturing activities and other activities. Administrative overheads in relation to production/manufacturing activities shall be included in the manufacturing cost. Administrative overheads in relation to marketing, projects management, corporate office or any other expense not related to the manufacturing activity shall be excluded from manufacturing cost.

4.3 Captive Consumption: Captive Consumption means the consumption of goods manufactured by one division or unit and consumed by another division or unit of the same organization or related undertaking for manufacturing another product(s), as defined in section 4(3) of the Central Excise Act, 1944.

4.4 Defectives: End Product and/or intermediate product units that do not meet quality standards. This may include reworks or rejects. An intermediate product is a product that might require further processing before it is saleable to the ultimate consumer.

4.4.1 Reworks: Defectives which can be brought up to the standards by putting in additional resources. Rework includes repairs, reconditioning, retro-fitment and refurbishing. 4.4.2 Rejects: Defectives which cannot meet the quality standards even after putting in additional resources. Rejects may be disposed off as waste or sold for salvage value or recycled in the production process.

4.5 Depreciation: Depreciation is a measure of the wearing out, consumption or other loss of value of a depreciable asset arising from use, efflux of time or obsolescence through technology and market changes. Depreciation does not include impairment loss. Depreciation is allocated so as to charge a fair proportion of the depreciable amount in each accounting period during the estimated useful life of the asset. Depreciable amount of a depreciable asset is its historical cost, or other amount substituted for historical cost in the financial statements, less the estimated residual value.

Manufacturing cost accounting encompasses areas that impact production operations and the valuation of inventory. These activities can significantly boost the profits of a business, as well as bring it into compliance with the applicable accounting standards. The cost accountant is primarily responsible for manufacturing accounting activities. The following are all elements of manufacturing cost accounting. The most critical is constraint analysis, since proper management of a company's constraint is the most important driver of its profitability.

Inventory Valuation:

This is the fully loaded cost of inventory at the end of an accounting period, which is required under various accounting standards to place a correct valuation on inventory. It is of little use in the day-to-day operations of the manufacturing area. Nonetheless, cost accountants spend a significant amount of time in this area, since a company's external auditors can be expected to spend a large amount of time reviewing inventory cost records. There are a number of ways to assign a valuation to inventory, such as the standard cost, FIFO, and LIFO methods.

Cost of Goods Sold Valuation:

This is closely related to inventory valuation. It is possible to track the cost of specific production jobs (job costing), or in general for all units produced (process costing). This cost tracking can be at the level of just those costs that vary with changes in revenue (direct costing), or it can include a full allocation of factory overhead costs (absorption costing).

Constraint Analysis:

This involves finding the bottleneck in the manufacturing process (if any) and advising the production department regarding the impact on throughput of changes to the flow of work through that bottleneck. The analysis can include an examination of the inventory buffer in front of the constraint and the existence of any upstream sprint capacity. This can be among the most important functions of manufacturing cost accounting.

Margin Analysis:

This involves the compilation of all costs associated with a product and subtracting them from product revenues to arrive at the margin of each product. Margin analysis can also be applied to distribution channels, business units, customers, and product lines. This is a traditional cost accounting role that is gradually giving way to constraint analysis, since many businesses now realize that incorporating allocated costs into margin analysis can lead to incorrect decisions to sell more or less of a product. Instead, it is better to consider that all products usually have some amount of throughput associated with them, so the real issue is to find the most profitable mix of products to produce (including the option to outsource production).

Variance Analysis:

This is the comparison of actual costs incurred to standard or budgeted costs, and exploring the reasons for any variances. This aspect of manufacturing cost accounting may not be necessary, since the baseline budget or standard cost may be faulty. Thus, a favorable variance may simply mean that a standard was set to be so easy to attain that all variances from it are bound to be favorable.

Budgeting

The information derived from the preceding analyses can be used as the basis for the annual budget for the manufacturing area, though this work is ultimately the responsibility of the production manager, not the cost accountant. The cost accountant will likely act as an advisor to the production manager in formulating the manufacturing budget.

Cost Accounting: Cost accounting is a systematic set of procedures manufacturers use for recording and reporting measurements of the cost of manufacturing goods and performing services. It includes methods for recognizing, classifying, allocating, aggregating and reporting such costs and comparing them with standard costs.

Cost accounting was originally developed to help manufacturers estimate the full costs of manufactured goods. “Costs” include the variable costs of the labor and raw materials needed for production, as well as the fixed costs. The total of these costs, divided by the number of units produced, represents the per-unit cost. As manufacturers increased the range of goods and services they provided and new technologies and management philosophies arose, costs became more difficult to assign.

Purpose of Cost Accounting:

An effective cost accounting system is needed to determine the “true” cost of a product, which is critical for all manufacturers in order to:

- Properly assign costs to inventory items for financial statement purposes.
- Determine sales price for products.
- Identify money makers/money losers.
- Compare different options for product mix
- Locate opportunities for cost improvement or reduction.
- Assist in the preparation and actualization of a business plan that includes an economic breakeven point.
- Improve strategic decision making.

How effective is Product Costing?

It's likely that many small or mid-sized manufacturers are putting themselves at considerable risk through the use of outdated costs if products have not been updated to take into account ongoing changes in the way the Company's products are made.

Consideration needs to be given to the cost impact of new technologies or recently-added business overhead. A periodic review should be conducted where individual product costs are reevaluated and overhead application rates and costing practices are adjusted accordingly.

The first step to determining how effective your product costing is involves a determination of what your most profitable and least profitable products and customers are. Communication with management and the sales department can go far to create a more profitable product mix and provide valuable input, whereby sales prices can be properly adjusted. Product profitability analysis drives corporate profitability; a function that is entirely controllable by management.

Methods of Cost Accounting:

There are several different cost accounting approaches that may be considered before implementing a cost accounting system. Traditional cost accounting is most effective for manufacturers with homogeneous products that have very few differences in the manufacturing process. This method assumes that there is a relationship between overhead and some volume-based measure, such as direct labor dollars/hours or machine hours. Advanced traditional cost accounting uses multiple factors as a base for allocating overhead and can significantly improve costing.

Activity-based costing is a practical tool that can be used by manufacturing companies of all sizes to not only better determine the cost of their products, but also to better understand why those products cost what they do.

Factors for Determination of Market Price:

When determining the right market price for your product, it's important to know what your competition is doing. Maintaining a history of your competition's pricing and price changes will assist you in anticipating their future decisions and allow you to react accordingly. Considering your customers' feedback is another valuable source of data to use in your pricing strategy. Your sales force should be seen as a resource to provide management with information related to customer satisfaction and for reactions on product quality and value.

In summary, understanding key factors impacting product costs and pricing is a critical function for any organization and will ensure that your organization has the information it needs to maintain or improve its competitive position.

The nature and functioning of business organizations in the modern business world have become very complicated. They have to serve the needs of variety of parties who are interested in the functioning of the business. These parties constitute the owners, creditors, employees, government agencies, tax authorities, prospective investors, and the management of the business. The business has to serve the needs of these different categories of people by way of supplying different information. In order to satisfy the needs of all these group of people a sound organization of cost accounting system is very essential.

Objective of the Research: The general objective of the study is to introduce an overview of cost accounting system and pricing policy of large-size and medium printing companies in Ethiopian. **Methodology of the Study** The researcher used both primary and secondary data. Primary data were collected from respondents through questionnaires and interviews. Secondary data were obtained from the enterprises' records, cost manuals and reports. Other secondary sources of data include books, journals, related websites in the internet, and other documents that are related to the topic under study. **Literature Review** The importance of accounting in managerial decisions has long been recognized in the literature. Particularly in the field of cost accounting, actual cost data, cost estimates and cost analysis. Cost data and analysis helps managers in making decisions in such areas like pricing, profit planning, setting standard cost, capital investment decisions, marketing decisions, cost management decisions and others. Historically, two costing methods, job order costing and process costing have been used to cost product and services and many companies continue to use these traditional costing systems (Garrison and Noreen, 2000). The job order costing system seeks to estimate costs of production for different jobs included in specific customer orders. Within organizations treating each job as a single output unit, or when multiple products are produced within a given period, this type of costing system is most relevant (Garrison, Noreen, & Brewer, 2008 and Atkinson, Kaplan, & Young, 2005). Horngren et al. (1999) defines Job costing as a costing system in which the cost of a product or service is obtained by assigning costs to a distinct unit, batch or lot of a product or service. Drury (1992) has described the procedures used in a job costing system and the accounting entries necessary to record the transactions taking place in a company using job costing. While analysing the various costing methods, he stated that job costing should be used when the company output is made of various jobs or orders from separate customers; he also stated that there are two alternative ways of designing a job costing system: either as an integrated cost accounting system or as an interlocking cost accounting system. Drury (1992) advocated the use of an integrated cost accounting system as this reduces or avoids the duplication of records as found in an interlocking system. Lucey (1993) also examined the mechanics of a costing system where job costing is employed. He first stated that this system must be used where the work to be performed is on customer's requirements. Secondly, this system must be based on good records obtained from production, works documentation, material and labor bookings.

The documents used here are the Material requisition forms, time tickets and the job cost sheet. Once prime costs have been gathered, overheads must be charged to jobs and this can be done using either the traditional methods based on the labour or machine hours overhead absorption rates or using the cost drivers rates of an activity-based system. He finally pinpointed that, for profits to be derived from a job costing system, it will depend on the costing technique used. Garrison and Noreen (2003) also contribute in the advancement of the knowledge on job costing. They first identified the type of industries where job costing can be used, namely: furniture, manufacturing, hospitals or legal firms. These are industries where the companies offer a wide variety of products or services.

From their point of view, material requisition forms, labour time tickets must be used for the assignment of direct materials and labour to the various jobs; then concerning the manufacturing overheads, they must be assigned using the predetermined overhead rates. The predetermined overhead rates generally use labour or machine time as the allocation bases. One area where cost analysis is used in managerial decision making is in setting product or services prices. Different pricing approaches are used by business organizations, which include cost-based pricing, market-based pricing, target pricing, and others. Also, business organizations are likely to adopt diverse pricing strategies. Noble and Gruca (1999) define pricing strategy as the means by which a pricing objective is to be achieved. Most pricing strategies imply a relative price level related to costs, competition, or customers. Determinants are the internal and external conditions that determine managers' choices of pricing strategies.

Results And Findings: This section provides analysis of the data gathered through questionnaire, interview and secondary data. The cost accounting system and pricing policy of the printing companies are classified under the following. There are as follows: -

1. Costing system,
2. Manufacturing cost,
3. Cost center,
4. Cost accumulation procedure,
5. Pricing policy and system.

Costing system: As indicated in the literature, costing system is needed to accumulate the costs of goods manufactured. The nature of production activities of printing companies warrants the use of customer order costing system since products are heterogeneous and are based on customer specifications. The customer order costing system is used by all printing companies in Ethiopia. Manufacturing cost Respondents were asked how the costs are classified, which costs are direct and indirect in calculating the cost of the product, how is the direct material cost charged and how material are priced in their companies.

The data is collected, classified and analyzed. According to the literature, manufacturing costs are commonly categorized as: direct material, direct labor and manufacturing overheads. According to the survey result, all printing companies in the study classify costs based on the nature of expense item as material cost, labor cost and manufacturing overhead. The material costs for major products (books, magazines, newspaper, commercial papers, administrative vouchers, stickers and note books) of the printing companies under study are composed of the cost of paper, ink, chemical, film, plate, staples and other supplies. Among those material costs, the cost of paper constitutes the direct material cost. The material cost for the product “Rubber Stamp” is composed of the cost of stamp handle, film, and chemicals. Stamp handle constitutes the direct material for the Rubber Stamp.

In general, paper and stamp handle constitute the direct materials of printing companies under study since the costs of paper and stamp handle are easily and economically identified with the specific products of the printing companies. In all printing companies under study, the direct material cost is charged to jobs by taking the cost of the item as per the stock card valuation. Materials are priced using weighted average costing method. The direct labor cost charged to products consists of the labor of machine operators (computer, camera, montage, cord, GTO, platine, speed master, stitching, web operators, etc.) which can be traced to specific printing products in an economically feasible way. The overhead cost is a summation of the cost of indirect materials (film, plate, ink, chemical, and other supplies), indirect labor (salaries of production manager, supervisors, quality controllers, janitors and maintenance), and all other manufacturing costs such as utility, depreciation, insurance etc, that cannot be charged directly to specific printing products. Cost Centers Respondents were asked the cost centers that exist in their production department.

The survey result indicates that a variety of cost centers are observed in the printing companies under study. The cost centers for the majority of the printing companies (101 companies, 84%) are: computer, camera, printing, platin, and binding. The cost centers for the remaining organizations (19 companies, 16%) are: computer, camera, cord, GTO, speed master, web, platin, cutter and stitching. Common cost centers observed in all printing companies under study are Computer, Camera, and Platin.

Cost Accumulation Procedures:An interview was conducted on the source documents used for cost accumulation purposes, how direct material cost, direct labor cost and manufacturing overhead cost was entered in the job order cost sheets. The data is collected and analyzed. The costs tracked and accumulated for product costing purposes are categorized as direct materials, direct labour, and manufacturing overheads. The direct material, direct labor and manufacturing overhead costs are accumulated for each job in a job cost sheet. Among the respondents in the study, 18% of them responded that the source documents (forms) they use for cost accumulation purpose are: production order, job order cost sheet, material requisition, material issue voucher, and labor time tickets.

Production orders are authorized by production managers to carry out jobs according to specific details indicated in the production order. The remaining 82% of the respondents under study responded that job order cost sheet, material requisition, material issue voucher and labor time tickets as basic source documents for accumulation of production costs. Direct Material Costs All the respondents stated that, the material requisition for job order costing will use the job order number given to the job order cost sheet. The materials to be used must be identified as direct materials and indirect materials. After the requisitions are segregated into direct and indirect materials, the direct materials consumption will be entered in the material section of the job order cost sheet.

Direct Labor Cost All respondents determine the direct labor cost of a product (job order) by multiplying an established direct labor rate by the actual direct labor hours consumed by the job. There is, however, some variation in the way the direct labor rate is determined by the printing companies. The survey result indicates that 36 percent of the respondents under study the variables considered in the determination of direct labor rate are: annual salary of operators, daily effective working hours, annual effective working days, and number of operators. The direct labor cost rate for a cost center is then determined as the annual salary of operators divided by the annual effective working hours.

The variables considered by the remaining 64 percent respondents in the determination of direct labor rate are: daily-salary of operators and the number of daily working hours. Accordingly, they compute the direct labor cost rate by dividing the daily-salary of operators by the number of daily working hours. The direct labor cost determined on the basis of the labor rate and the actual direct labor consumed is then recorded in the job cost sheet. The direct labor rates differ from cost center to cost center. The total direct labor cost for a product (job) is then the sum of all the direct labor costs accumulated in the cost centers where the product is processed.

Manufacturing Overhead: Manufacturing overhead costs are difficult to trace to each job and are usually predetermined. Respondents were asked the different overhead rate prepared. According to the survey result 18 percent of the printing companies under study determine three rates: Manufacturing Overhead Rate, Selling and Distribution Expense Rate, and General and Administrative Expense Rate. The remaining 82 percent companies determine and use only manufacturing overhead rate. Respondents were also asked the basis used for overhead cost allocations. The basis used for overhead cost allocation was investigated in one of the questions pertaining to manufacturing overhead.

Responses were reported in table:

Basis used for overhead cost allocation

Basis used	Frequency	Percent
Direct labor hours	91	76
Both direct labour and machine hours	29	24
Total	120	100

Source: Primary data The survey result indicates that in setting the pre-determined manufacturing overhead rate, 24 percent of the printing companies use direct labor hour as a base for setting the predetermined rates for the labor intensive operations (computer and camera cost centers) and use machine hours as a base for the machine intensive operations (Cord; GTO; Speed master; Web; Platin; and Binding cost centers). The remaining 76 percent use direct labor hour as a base for setting the predetermined manufacturing overhead rates for all cost centers.

The manufacturing overhead cost applied to jobs is captured (recorded) in the job cost sheet. Pre-determined overhead rates differ from cost center to cost center. The manufacturing overhead cost for a product (job) is then the sum of all the applied factory overhead costs accumulated in the cost centers where the product is processed. General and administration expense rate is the expense of finance, planning and marketing research, administration and manager's office. The administrative expense rate is developed according to the share of manufacturing cost as a whole. So that administration expense is charged to a job accordingly. Selling and distribution expense rate are expenses incurred under commercial department and developed based on the share of manufacturing cost so that it is charged to a job similarly.

The General and Administration Expense Rate and the Selling and Distribution Expense Rate are determined by relating the expenses to the total manufacturing costs as follows:

General and Administration Expense Rate =
Actual General and Administration Expenses of the previous year /
Total Manufacturing Costs of the previous year.

Selling and Distribution Expense Rate = Actual Selling and Distribution Expense of the previous year/Total Manufacturing Costs of the previous year.

Pricing Policy and System: Survey respondents were asked the pricing policy of their companies. Regarding the pricing policy of printing companies, the survey result shows that all of the printing companies under study use cost-plus pricing method. Thus, the findings indicate that the pricing policy of printing companies under study has close relation with the product costs.

Interviews were made with the marketing managers about the different strategy of setting prices. All marketing managers used a strategy of setting high prices in the case of security products and lower prices for other products. The volume of orders also influences prices. Large volumes lead to lower unit prices. In setting selling prices for products, the survey result shows that all of the respondents under study consider each cost component: the material cost of a product, labor cost of a product, and overhead cost of a product as per the data provided by the Finance Department.

The direct material cost of a product is estimated based on the customer specification or sample. On the basis of the specifications or sample, the required list of materials and the respective quantities are derived by the Estimation Section. The estimated quantities of materials are multiplied by unit costs given by the Finance Department to determine the material cost. The direct labor cost is charged to each product on a rating basis. The direct labor hours of the job order (product) in each cost center are estimated in advance jointly by the Commercial Department and Production department. To determine the total direct labor cost incurred on a product, each cost center direct labor cost is added to arrive at the total direct labor cost of a product. The total manufacturing overhead costs applied to a product is determined by summing up each cost center manufacturing overhead cost applied.

The approach used by 86 percent of the printing companies under study in setting the selling price is as follows:

Direct material cost + Direct Labor cost + Manufacturing over head cost = Total Cost + Profit margin + VAT = Selling price

14 percent of the sampled printing companies use a different approach in determining the total cost of a product and setting the price. These companies include selling and distribution expense and general and administrative expenses in the total cost of a product using allocation rates.

Thus, the method of setting the selling price of a product is as follows:

Direct material cost + Direct Labor cost + Manufacturing over head cost + Selling and distribution expenses + General and Administration expenses = Total Cost + Profit margin + VAT = Selling price.

Conclusion: Costing system is needed to accumulate the costs of goods manufactured. The nature of production activities of printing companies warrants the use of customer order costing system since products are heterogeneous and are based on customer specifications. Controllers, janitors and maintenance), and all other manufacturing costs such as utility, depreciation, insurance etc, that cannot be charged directly to specific printing products.

Common cost centers observed in all printing companies are Computer, Camera, and Platin. The direct material, direct labor and manufacturing overhead costs are accumulated for each job in a job cost sheet. Regarding the pricing policy of printing companies, the survey result shows that all of the printing companies under study use cost-plus pricing method. Thus, the findings indicate that the pricing policy of printing companies under study has close relation with the product costs.

Paper and stamp handle constitute the direct materials since the costs of paper and stamp handle are easily and economically identified with the specific products of the printing companies. Furthermore, the direct labor cost charged to products consists of the labor of machine operators (computer, camera, montage, cord, GTO, platine, speed master, stitching, web operators, etc.) which can be traced to specific printing products in an economically feasible way. The overhead cost is a summation of the cost of indirect materials (film, plate, ink, chemical, and other supplies), indirect labor (salaries of production manager, supervisors, quality.

Review of Literature: In this section, related literatures on the subject matter are briefly reviewed with a view to showing vividly the gap in knowledge and for easy interpretation of the research result. It reviews definition cost by many authors in their book, the element of cost and also define cost accounting in brief. This section presents the review of related literatures in order to establish a basis for the application of cost accounting practice.

Definition of Cost: Cost is the measurement of the sacrifice of economic resources that has already been made or is to be made in the future, in order to achieve a specific objective (Shim & Siegel, 2000, p. 2). Cost can be defined as the value of inputs that have been used to produce something, or the value measured by what must be given, done, or undergone to obtain something. Measuring costs is the second most important thing accountants do, right after measuring profit (Trcy & Laurin, 2007, p. 221). Usually the term “Cost” is used as an alternative with the term “Expense”. Expense can be defined as a measured outflow of goods or services: The costs of the materials or services used to produce the revenue (Syme, Ireland & Dodds, 2013, p. 140). Actually, the terms cost and expense have been used by accountants, economists, and engineers according to their needs. Accountants have defined cost as an exchange price, a forgoing, a sacrifice made to secure benefit.

Cost is defined as an economic resource related to manpower, equipment, real facilities, supplies and all other resources that required to accomplish work activities or to produce output (Stewart, 1 995a). Usually costs are stated in terms of monetary value. Therefore, costs are the value of money which represents the resources paid for the production of the output.

Elements of Cost: Lall Nigam, BM. & Jain, IC. (2001) puts together a framework for classifying total costs by five bases, which are behavioral, functional, responsibility, traceability and relevance to decision-making. The “Behavioral” classification measures the changes in costs in relation to the changes in level of activity.

Three categories are Fixed, Variable, and Semi-Variable.

➤ Fixed Costs: are those that remain constant regardless of the volume of output within a certain level. They are also called capacity costs as they denote the productive capacity. Thus when the range of activity expands beyond the peak capacity, the current fixed costs rise to another level, which is termed step costs. A sub-division of fixed costs is committed fixed costs and discretionary fixed costs (also known as programmed/managed fixed costs). The former involve the acquisition and maintenance of the organization and its long-term assets, e.g. depreciation of equipment, rental of buildings, and key personnel salaries. Whilst the latter can be manipulated by management and adjust to situations, e.g. research and development (R&D), public relations, training initiatives.

➤ Variable Cost: Variable cost is the cost of elements which tends to directly vary with the volume of activity. Variable cost has two parts (i) Variable direct cost (ii) Variable indirect costs. Variable indirect costs are termed as variable overheads. Example: Direct labor, Outward Freight...etc.

➤ Semi-Variable Costs: Semi variable costs contain both fixed and variable elements. They are partly affected by fluctuation in the level of activity. These are partly fixed and partly variable costs and vice versa. Example: Factory supervision, Maintenance...etc. The “Functional” classification is based on the purpose of activities undertaken. It is divided into Manufacturing and Non-Manufacturing categories. Direct material cost, direct labor cost and manufacturing overhead costs are classified under manufacturing costs whereas selling & distribution costs and administrative & office costs classified as non-manufacturing costs.

Manufacturing Costs: comprise of every cost in the plant up to the point when goods are finished, i.e. direct material, direct labor, and factory overheads.

DMC: Direct manufacturing material costs include the acquisition of materials with their related costs that can be directly traced. Some examples of direct materials are cloth is row material for making garments, timber for making furniture, etc.

DLC: Direct manufacturing labor costs include the compensation of all manufacturing labor that can be traced to the cost object that is work in process and then finished goods in an economically feasible way. For conversion of raw material into finished goods, human resource is needed, and such human resource is termed as labor. Labor cost is the main element of cost in a product or service. Direct labor cost is easily traceable to specific products. Direct labor costs are specially and conveniently traceable to specific products. Direct labor varies directly with the volume of output.

MOHC: Costs other than direct material and direct labor cost which are not clearly associated with specific product are manufacturing overhead costs. Overheads include the cost of indirect material, indirect labor and indirect expenses. The major category of overhead costs is operation overhead and general and administrative overhead. Manufacturing overhead costs are costs incurred in the factory for production of goods and services. These include all indirect material like grease, oil, cost of tread etc., indirect labor like salary for factory managers, salary of warehouse man and indirect expenses incurred in the factory such as rent for factory building, power and fuel used in the factory, insurance of factory building etc.

Non-Manufacturing Costs: There are three types of Non-Manufacturing Costs. Administrative costs relate to organizing and controlling the operations, hence are largely fixed in nature, e.g. key personal and clerical staff salaries, electricity bill and equipment of general office. Marketing costs include selling and distribution. The former are costs spent on creating demand and securing orders, e.g. sales staff's salaries, advertising, market research. Whilst the latter are the costs to move the goods from the plant to customers, e.g. warehouse, vehicles, wages of packers and drivers. Lastly financing costs are paid for raising and using capitals, e.g. loan interest, fees for issuing shares, bonds coupons.

Thirdly, costs are classified in terms of "Managers' Responsibility" into controllable and non-controllable categories.

- Controllable Costs: are those that managers are capable to exert influence on as well as responsible for.
 - Non-Controllable Costs: are those that are under the managers' supervision, however, cannot be influenced by their actions. One important notion for this notion of control is the point of reference, and managers should only be held liable for costs that are under his/her control. Cost is the cost which is not subject to control at any level of managerial supervision.
 - The fourth classification is based on the "Costs' Traceability" to a specific product, job, or process. Firstly, those that can be conveniently assigned are called Direct Costs, e.g. material and labor engaged in manufacturing a product. There are also costs that cannot find a single cause which are called Indirect Costs, e.g. plant manager salary, depreciation of machines and plant.

- According to this criterion for classification, material cost is divided into direct material cost and indirect material cost, Labor cost is divided into direct labor and indirect labor cost and expenses into direct expenses and indirect expenses. Indirect cost is also known as overhead. Direct Material Cost: Cost of material which can be directly allocated to a cost centre or a cost object in an economically feasible way. Direct labor Cost: Cost of wages of those workers who are readily identified or linked with a cost centre or cost object.

Direct Expenses: Expenses other than direct material and direct labour which can be identified or linked with cost centre or cost object. Direct Material + Direct labor + Direct Expenses = Prime Cost Indirect Material: Cost of material which cannot be directly allocable to a particular cost centre or cost object. Indirect Labor: Cost of wages of employees which are not directly allocable to a particular cost centre. Indirect expenses: Expenses other than of the nature of material or labor and cannot be directly allocable to a particular cost centre. Indirect Material + Indirect Labor + Indirect Expenses = Overheads Lastly, in order to facilitate with management's decision-making, two classifications are made.

One is classifying the costs against revenue and used to determine income and prepare financial statements, which include Product Cost and Period Cost. All the costs incurred to manufacture the finished product belong to product cost, i.e. direct material and labor, variable factory overheads. Products costs are initially recorded under 'asset', then are transferred to 'cost of goods sold' once the finished products are sold to customers. On the other hand, period costs are immediately expensed as they occur, typically those costs that are fixed in nature, hence show its effect on the income statement of the corresponding accounting period. Another way is to classify costs into Relevant and Irrelevant Costs.

A. Relevant Costs: are defined as "future incremental costs to be affected by current decisions". Three elements include differential costs, opportunity costs, and out-of-pocket costs.

➤ Differential Cost: Differential cost is the change in the cost due to change in activity from one level to another.

➤ Opportunity Cost: Opportunity cost is the value of alternatives foregone by adopting a particular strategy or employing resources in specific manner. It is the return expected from 13 an investment other than the present one. These refer to costs which result from the use or application of material, labor or other facilities in a particular manner which has been foregone due to not using the facilities in the manner originally planned. Resources (or input) like men, materials, plant and machinery, finance etc., when utilized in one particulars way, yield a particular return (or output). If the same input is utilized in another way, yielding the same or a different return, the original return on the forsaken alternative that is no longer obtainable is the opportunity cost.

For example, if fixed deposits in the bank are proposed to be withdrawn for financing project, the opportunity cost would be the loss of interest on the deposits. Similarly when a building leased out on rent to a party is got vacated for own purpose or a vacant space is not leased out but used internally, say, for expansion of the production programmed, the rent so forgone is the opportunity cost.

➤ **Out-of-Pocket Cost:** This is the portion of the cost associated with an activity that involve cash payment to other parties, as opposed to costs which do not require any cash outlay, such as depreciation and certain allocated costs. Out-of-Pocket Costs are very much relevant in the consideration of price fixation during trade recession or when a make-or-buy decision is to be made.

Irrelevant Costs: are those costs that will not change regardless of the decision made, e.g. sunk costs.

Sunk Costs: Sunk costs are historical costs which are incurred i.e. sunk in the past and are not relevant to the particular decision making problem being considered. Sunk costs are those that have been incurred for a project and which will not be recovered if the project is terminated. While considering the replacement of a plant, the depreciated book value of the old asset is irrelevant as the amount is sunk cost which is to be written-off at the time of replacement.

Meaning of Cost Accounting: Cost accounting is a formal system of accounting for costs in the books account by means of which costs of products and services are ascertained and controlled. Cost accounting is the mathematical approximation or economic calculation of resources (including the durables, working time, space, knowledge and ideas) consumed by accost object during the course manufacturing products or providing services (Kohler, 2007). 14 Cost accounting as an information processing system includes a series of ordered and logically connected activities.

The key purpose of these activities consists in translating data on the use of resources involved in the company's operations into information which reflects the costs of specified reference objects (Nowak and Wierzbinski, 2010).

Cost accounting is the process of accumulating the costs of manufacturing, and other functional processes and identifying these costs with units produced or some other object. It is a unique sub filed of managerial and financial accounting. Cost accounting is applied primarily to manufacturing. Organization that combine and process raw material in to finished products. Cost accounting is the process of measuring, analyzing, and reporting financial and nonfinancial information related to the costs of acquiring or using resources in an organization. For example, calculating the cost of a product is a cost accounting function that meets both the financial accountant's inventory-valuation needs and the management accountant's decision making needs (such as deciding how to price products and choosing which products to promote).

However, today most accounting professionals take the perspective that cost information is part of the management accounting information collected to make management decisions. Thus, the distinction between management accounting and cost accounting is not so clear-cut. (Horngren et al, 2018). Cost accounting can help management by analyzing statistical data, establishing costing methods and procedures that control cost, ascertaining company costs and profit, and selecting from two or more alternatives that might increase or decrease revenue or cost respectively.”

The objective of any organization is represented by the increase of revenue & the decrease of costs”. (Jinga, Dumitru, Dumitrana & Vulpoi, 2010, P, 243). The main objective of cost accounting, therefore, is to minimize expenditure and maximize profit. An effective cost management system is essential in pursuing future growth and maintaining an optimal level of costs(Kwan, 2011, p. 23).

Cost accounting, in fact, helps management in making strategic decisions by identifying an organization comparative strength & weakness & better ways to use them.” Cost accounting supplies cost data & information to management to make more informed decision”. (Rani & Kidance, 2012, p. 202).

Purpose of Cost Accounting: The cost accounting in its developed form helps the management of manufacturing concerns in improving the efficiency, in making the business decisions and in evaluating the performance of entities in the same industrial sector through standardizing the systems and procedures. (Hussain, 2009, p. 43)

The main objectives of cost accounting are as follows (Samaha and Abdallah , 2011):

- ❖ **Ascertainment of Cost:** This is the primary objective of cost accounting. For cost ascertainment, different techniques and systems of cost accounting are used under different circumstance.
- ❖ **Control of Cost:** Cost control aims at improving efficiency by controlling and reducing cost. It is becoming increasingly important because of growing completion. Guide to business policy-cost data provides guidelines for various managerial decisions like make or buy, selling below cost, utilization of idle plant capacity, and introduction of a new product.
- ❖ **Determination of Selling Price:** cost accounting provides cost information on the basis of which selling prices of products or services may be fixed. In periods of depression, cost accounting guides in deciding the extent to which the selling prices may be reduced to meet the situation.

- ❖ Determine and Control Efficiency: Measuring and improving the performance of cost accounting measures efficiency by classifying and analyzing cost data and then suggest various steps improving performance so that profitability is increased.

- ❖ Determine the value of closing inventory for preparing financial statements of the concern.

- ❖ Provide a basis for operating policies which may be determination of Cost Volume relationship, whether to close or operate at a loss, whether to manufacture or buy from market, whether to continue the existing method of production or to replace it by a more improved method of production....etc

Cost Accounting Practices: According to, historians have long endorsed the view that cost accounting is a product of the industrial revolution (Jonson, 2001). For example (Wilson and Chua, 2003) claimed that cost accounting was practiced by the mechanized multi process, cotton textile factories that appeared in England and United States around 1800. This point of view was consistent with Garner (2004) who pointed out that cost accounting had emerged only after eighteenth century as a result of the rise of the factory system in the industrial revolution The traditional view contained that cost accounting arose due to the increase use of fixed capital prompted accountants during the industrial revolution to graft cost accounting on the double entry system (Johnson, 2001).

The evolution of cost accounting is a single in to three eras-the first era from the first appearance until before the industrialization; the second from the industrialization to the twentieth century and there after the third (Antonelli and Vetal, 2009). During the first era, the nomenclature cost accounting might not exist as a clear and well recognized concept like it is today, the activity could be called by other names. The first point appearance of cost accounting can be traced back to the fourteenth century (Thukaram, 2012). With the expansion of the scale of business, mainly in manufacturing activities that small enterprises started to produce trade items such as books, woolens, coins and wine, an expansion in cost accounting was required (Cunagin and Stancil , 2002). Modern business firms utilize a variety of cost accounting practices in an effort to manage expenditures and maximize profits (King, Premo, & Cas , 2009, p. 21)All business enterprises try to maximize profit margin by controlling expenditures.

A cost accounting department can minimize the costs by providing all necessary information to management. A manufacturing company's income statement is more complex than a retailer or a merchandiser as it transforms raw materials into finished goods through the use of labor. As a result of manufacturing goods, manufacturers must understand the various costs associated with this production process. It is simply not sufficient to know the price paid for raw materials when manufacturing a finished product. The cost accounting system used by a manufacturing company should be able to provide information relevant for the external reporting system.

For a manufacturing firm, financial reporting separates costs based on when those costs become recognized as expenses. All costs manufacturers can be classified as product or period costs. Product costs are frequently referred to as manufacturing costs. These costs are assigned specifically to units of production and recognized as an expense when product is sold. As such, product costs follow the product through inventory and are recorded as an asset in the inventory system. Period costs include all other manufacturing costs. These costs are expensed as they are incurred (Lanen, Andorsen and Maher, 2008).

Techniques of Costing: It is important for businesses to adopt and utilize cost accounting methods that fully recognize cost and allow for innovation within the company (Kawan, 2011). In developing an effective cost accounting system; executives can apply several techniques that will undoubtedly assist in the operations of the organization. Executives should understand the importance of these methods in producing one efficient cost accounting system that will help cut costs and produce quality outputs.

Techniques that management can utilize to develop a better cost accounting system to compete in the global market include standard costing, target costing, ABC and the just in time approach (Hansen, 2009), Traditional Costing, Standard Costing

It refers to the preparation of standard costs and applying them to measure the variations from standard costs and analyzing the variations with a view to maintain maximum efficiency in production. What is done in this case is that costs of each article are determined before-hand under current and anticipated conditions, but sometimes they are determined before-hand under normal or ideal conditions. Then actual costs are compared with the predetermined costs and deviations known as variances are noted down. Thereafter, the reasons for the variances are ascertained and necessary steps are taken to prevent their recurrence.

Standard costing is one of the most known and widely used product costing systems. Standard costing is a widely used accounting system because it can create information for a lot of purposes: decision-making purposes, providing challenging targets to achieve, assists on setting budgets, acts as a control device by highlighting unwanted activities and simplifies the task of tracing costs to products for profit measurement and inventory valuation purposes (Drury 2004). In manufacturing companies, the procedures often are of a repetitive nature and therefore standard costing is pertinent in these kinds of companies.

Control is activated by the use of different budgets. The methods of standard costing are used in order to make a solution for different limitations of historical costing. Historical costing which refers to ascertainment of costs after they have been incurred provides the management with an account of what has been happened. "Standard costing methods involve the preparation and use of standard costs, their comparison with actual costs and analysis of the deviations to their causes so as to provide corrective actions (Sikka, 2003)."

Standard costing is financial control system that enables the deviations from the budget to be analyzed more effectively (Drury, 2012). He further stated that standard costs are preset costs; they are target costs that should be incurred under efficient operating circumstances. Mainly, standard costing is a method of cost control in which cost data for activity are presented based on the formal level of operation (Larry and Crosphopher, 2009). A standard cost is a carefully determined cost of a unit of output (Horgren, 2012).

According to Drury (2012), in the application of standard costing system, the standard costs for the actual output for a specific period are traced out by the managers of responsibility centers who are accountable for the operations. When it comes to the actual cost for the same period the costs are charged to the responsibility center. Therefore, the actual and the standard costs are compared and the deviation between them reported. For simple controlling costs, the usage of a standard costing system is beneficial for companies.

The main reasons to develop standard costing system are that helps executive manage costs, improve planning and control, facilitate decision making, and facilitate product costing (Hansen, 2009).¹⁹ In this system, products costs are determined by using quantitative and price standards for materials, labor and overhead. For many tons, the use standard costing variance analysis has been viewed as the most effective tool for cost control (Kinney, 2006).

Target Costing: The term target cost is the difference between the sales price needed to capture a predetermined market share and the desired per unit profit (Hansen, 2009). This difference is the allowable cost that managers permit for the cost of the product. In this process, management must find cost reductions if current costs are higher than the target cost. This ensures that management changes the operations of the entire business in order to achieve such results. Target costing is a management tool for reducing the overall cost of an output through its product life cycle (Jalae, 2012). Target costing creates the relationship between cost, price and profit. (Helms, Etkin, Baxter and Gordon, 2005) stated that target costing is not like cost reduction techniques or control outline, but it is a part of total strategic profit management system including value analysis and value engineering. It begins with a targeted sales price of a product. It is different from traditional pricing approach which centered on developing a product, then determining the expected cost based on the expected volume and the setting a selling price.

However, in target costing approach the company determines a selling price that the customer willing to pay and the desired profit margin deducted from selling price and the maximum target cost known. Jalae (2012) stated that target costing is a mechanism that exploiting cost information and it aims at on the better price leader and it prevents time wastage on the discussion regarding design and re-engineering of the product. It is based on examining all elements of costs related to possessing the product through all stages of its life cycle.

These elements include the purchase price, operating costs, operating supplies and repair and maintenance costs. The objective of target costing system is to reduce the cost of the life cycle of the product.

Activity-Based Costing (ABC): It is a cost accounting system that focuses on an organization's activities and collects costs on the basis of the underlying nature and extent of those activities. Multiple predetermined overhead rates are then calculated using the various cost drivers of organizational activities. ABC focuses on attaching costs to products and services based on the activities conducted to produce, perform, distribute, and support those products and services. The three fundamental components of activity-based costing are: • Recognizing that costs are incurred at different organizational levels, • Accumulating costs into related cost pools, and • Using multiple cost drivers to assign costs to products and services. (Michael & Cecily, 2011) An ABC system is a cost accounting system that uses both unit and non-unit based cost drivers to assign costs to cost objects by first tracing costs to activities and then tracing costs from activities to products (Hasenn, 2009). In ABC accounting, the system attempts to reveal costs through direct tracing instead of allocation. This creates a more accurate picture of the total costs associated with a product. Besides reducing costs, this management tool also improves the final price that customers pay for the product by focusing on the activity involved. The philosophy behind using ABC is the value that it provides to customers at a cost less than the price customers pay for that value.

Method of Cost System: The two basic types of costing systems are used to assign cost to product or service. Some of them are as follows: 2.8.1. Job Order Costing System In this system the cost object is a unit or multiple unit of a distinct product or service called a job. Job order costing system is a type of cost system that provides for a separate record of the cost of each particular quantity of product that passes through the factory. Job order costing system is commonly used by companies with product that are unique and divisible. In this system costs are assigned to a distinct unit, batch or lot of product, or service. Job is task for which resources expended in bringing a distinct product or services to market (Cherington, 2008, P, 277). Job order costing is method of ascertaining cost in those industries in which goods are manufactured or services rendered against specific order from customers. A job order cost system manufacturing accumulates costs of material, labor and manufacturing overhead expense by specific orders, jobs, batches or lots. Job costing system is a method in which cost object is a unit or multiple units of a distinct product or service called a job. Job order costing system are widely used in construction, furniture, printing and similar industries where the costs of a specific job depend on the particular order specification (Williamsan, 2009). Examples of business that use job order costing includes Construction system, Furniture manufactures Printing firms, Repair shops, Service giving organization, Garages, etc

Process Costing System: This costing system is used for manufacturing process which produces a single product or single mix of products continuously for an extended period of time. In this system the cost of a product or service is obtained by using broad averages to assign cost to mass of similar units produced for general sale and not for any specific customers. Average cost over large number of nearly identical product companies that use process costing system are as follow Cherrington, 2008, P 278).

- ✓ Cement factories
- ✓ Petroleum refineries
- ✓ Flour companies
- ✓ Beer factories
- ✓ Textile factories
- ✓ Beverage companies.

In this system, the cost object is masses of identical or similar units of a product or service. The focus of a process cost system is the cost center to which costs are assigned. It is usually a department, but it could be a process or an operation. Costs accumulated by a cost center are divided by the number of units produced in that cost center to compute the cost per unit. The primary objectives, like that of the job order cost system, are to compute the unit cost of the products completed and the cost to be assigned to the ending work in process inventory (Vanderbeck, 2010).

In manufacturing process costing setting, each unit receives the same or similar amounts of direct material costs, direct labor costs and indirect manufacture costs (Horngren, 2003). According to Arora (2003), processes costing system follow the following procedures: First, the factory is divided in to a number of processes and an account is maintained for each process. Second, each process account is debited with material cost, labor cost, and direct expenses and overhead allocated or apportioned to the process. Third, the output of a process is transferred to the next process in the sequence. Finally, the finished output of the last process is transferred to the finished goods account.

Cost Control: Cost Control is defined as the regulation by executive action of the costs of operating an undertaking, particularly where such action is guided by Cost Accounting. Agara (2005) opines that cost control is a process whereby targets are set against which the daily incidence of cost is compared to ensure that cost targets are not unduly exceeded. Adeniyi (2007) specified that cost control the standard of cost of operating an organization and it is concerned with holding costs within tolerable limit. He said this limits will regularly in a form operational plan or budget.

Cost control action will be important, if actual cost vary from planed cost by too much amount. He further explained that is a process of setting targets and receiving feedback information in order to ensure that actual performance is in line with set target and if not, take corrective action.

They further explained that cost control is used to define the activities of manager in short-run and long-run planning and management of costs. They further proceed that planning and cost control is often inseparably related with revenue and profit planning.

Cost control involves the following steps and covers the various facets of the management:

- ❖ **Planning:** First step in cost control is establishing plans / targets. The plan/target may be in the form of budgets, standards, estimates and even past actual may be expressed in physical as well as monetary terms. These serves as yardsticks by which the planned objective can be assessed.
- ❖ **Communication:** The plan and the policy laid down by the management are made known to all those responsible for carrying them out. Communication is established in two directions; directives are issued by higher level of management to the lower level for compliance and the lower level executives report performances to the higher level.
- ❖ **Motivation:** The plan is given effect to and performances starts. The performance is evaluated, costs are ascertained and information about results achieved are collected and reported. The fact that costs are being complied for measuring performances acts as a motivating force and makes individuals endeavor to better their performances.
- ❖ **Appraisal and Reporting:** The actual performance is compared with the predetermined plan and variances, i.e. deviations from the plan are analyzed as to their causes. The variances are reported to the proper level of management.
- ❖ **Decision Making:** The variances are reviewed and decisions taken. Corrective actions and remedial measures or revision of the target, as required, are taken. In the process of manufacturing companies, the concern of cost control management is essential in order to effectively utilize the material resources. In addition to this, cost control includes the management measures implemented to ensure that cost continues in accordance with the management plan. The significance of cost control cannot be over emphasized as an existence technique for manufacturing companies because they ensure appropriate monitoring of cost against budget and correct any financially impropriety of the company. The term cost control is used widely and no uniform definition exists (Horngren et. al, 2012).

Cost Reduction: Cost reduction may be defined as the real and permanent reduction in the unit costs of goods manufactured or services rendered without impairing their suitability for the use intended. As will be seen from the definition, the reduction in costs should be real and permanent.

Reductions due to windfalls, fortuitous receipts, changes in government policy like reduction in taxes or duties, or due to temporary measures taken for tiding over the financial difficulties do not strictly come under the purview of cost reduction. At the same time a program of cost reduction should in no way affect the quality of the products nor should it lower the standards of performance of the business. 24 A systematic process used by companies to reduce their cost without having negative impact on quality product or service. CIMA(2005) indicated that cost reduction is the achievement of real and permanent reduction in the unit of cost of goods manufactured or service rendered without impairing their suitability from the use of intended for or diminution in the quality of products.

Real and permanent cost reduction can be achieved through mass production, lower price input, simplifying the manufacturing process without sacrificing the quality products, implementing best practice, elimination of wastage and duplication of work the production process. Cost reduction is a continuous process of critically examining various elements of cost in each aspect of business operation and improving policy and procedure manuals, work instructions, work flow diagrams operation management and improving efficiency or optimal utilization resources. Profit is the resultant of two varying factors, viz., sales and cost.

The wider the gap between these two factors, the larger is the profit. Thus, profit can be maximized either by increasing sales or by reducing costs. In a competition less market or in case of monopoly products, it may perhaps be possible to increase price to earn more profits and the need for reducing costs may not be felt. Such conditions cannot, however, exist paramount and when competition comes into play, it may not be possible to increase the sale price without having its adverse effect on the sale volume, which, in turn, reduces profit. Besides, increase in price of products has the ultimate effect of pushing up the raw material prices, wages of employees and other expenses all of which tend to increase costs. In the long run, substitute products may come up in the market, resulting in loss of business. Avenues have, therefore, to be explored and method devised to cut down expenditure and thereby reduce the cost of products. In short, cost reduction would mean maximization of profits by reducing cost through economics and savings in costs of manufacture, administration, selling and distribution.

Use of Cost Information: Manufacturing organizations assign costs to products for two purposes:

First, for internal profit measurement and external financial accounting requirements in order to allocate the manufacturing costs incurred during a period between cost of goods sold and inventories.

Second, it uses to provide useful information for managerial decision making requirements. In order to meet financial accounting requirements, it may not be necessary to accurately trace costs to individual products (Drury and Tayles, 2005).

With knowledge of the fixed costs and variable costs, the manager should use this information, along with the financial statements, to aid in the decision making process. The traditional income statement is primarily used for external reporting. The value approach or the contribution margin income statement is more useful for internal decision making (Lanen, Anderson, and Maher, 2010).

Companies can use cost information for two purposes;

A. Cost for planning & control: A company of information system provides the data required for the preparation and operation of budget and for establishing standard costs.

B. Cost for analytical purpose: Different type of involve varying kind of consideration in managerial analysis for decision making for example different analysis for decision making.

Spoilage, Rework and Scrap: AS (Hornngren et al 2016) explained; the terms Spoilage, Rework, and Scrap are not interchangeable. For a financial accountant, the costs must be classified differently because under ASPE/IFRS different transactions give rise to each type of cost. Some amount of spoilage, rework, or scrap is an inherent part of many production processes. Rework is the conversion of production rejects into reusable products of the same or lower quality. Scrap is a residual material that results from manufacturing a product. Scrap has minimal total sales value compared with the total sales value of the product. In some situations the firm may have to pay to have the scrap removed. In this case, it is usually referred to as waste or refuse.

Spoilage refers to output that fails to attain either a specified performance level or standard of composition. To minimize cost, managers want to determine the costs of spoilage and distinguish between the costs of normal and abnormal spoilage.

Normal Spoilage arises under efficient operating conditions as a result of predictable rates of failure in a production process. Normal spoilage may be a locked-in cost, which managers accept when they invest in equipment with a specific failure rate. These costs are not considered controllable or avoidable. IFRS permits the costs of normal spoilage to be included in the costs of goods manufactured (COGM). The cost is transferred to cost of goods sold when the good units are sold. The normal spoilage rate should be computed using the total good units completed as the base, not the total actual units started (into production/process), because total units started also includes any abnormal spoilage in addition to normal spoilage.

Abnormal Spoilage is spoilage that is unexpected under efficient operating conditions but is regarded as controllable and avoidable. The cost of abnormal spoilage can extend well beyond the immediate cost of the offending product. Abnormal spoilage costs are written off as losses of the accounting period in which detection of the spoiled units occurs.

For the most informative internal feedback, the Loss from Abnormal Spoilage account should appear in a detailed statement of comprehensive income as a separate line item and not be buried as an indistinguishable part of the COGM.

Empirical Literature Review: Previously different researchers were worked on the title of “Assessment of Cost Management Practice”; most of these papers were focused on manufacturing industry. The researchers assessed different organizations cost accounting practice and made conclusion according to their observation Some of them are; Girum ketema and his teammate were worked on the title of the “assessment of cost accounting practice in kality food Share Company” in 2014; the objective of the paper was to assess and examine the product costing system of the company under study to identify the real causes of why the main research problem is occurring. Based on the objectives of researchers to conclude The current product costing system, cost center allocation, and cost allocation base are found at good level with the existence of some problem, also kality food s.c. use proper controlling mechanism for handling and keeping of cost related transactions. 27 Alemu Feleke were worked on same title in national alcohol & liquor factory in 2019, the objective of the study is to asses cost accounting practices in control and reducing in manufacturing cost.

The researcher was gathered the data through a combination of both unstructured interviews with the department head and questionnaire addressed to the employees of the organization. The data received were analyzed by using narration and descriptive statistics. Finally he concludes that the company does not give chance for employees to participate in budget preparation and standard setting, it does not use target costing as cost control and reduction tools and techniques and reporting without relating of actual and planned information. Lack of assign costs to particular cost objects and each cost object has not separate measurement of cost, use only traditional costing method and giving cost information for external users. An analysis conducted by (Samaha K. and Abdallah S., 2011), entitled A comparative analysis of ABC and traditional costing system:

The case of Egyptian metal industries company compares ABC results with traditional accounting (volume based) ones in an Egyptian metal industry company; In fact traditional accounting can lead to price distortion. In particular, the study highlights that volume based methods underestimate low volume products and overestimate high volume products while ABC, tracing overhead consumption, lead to more precise results. Meskud Arebo also worked on the same title in Kality food share co. in 2011 at Jimma University; the objective was to assess the product costing system of the factory.

To achieve this objective, the researcher were used both primary, and secondary data sources. Primary data were obtained using in-depth interview where as secondary data were obtained from annuals, records and financial statements of the factory. The researcher concludes that the company uses both process costing and job order costing system.

The basic Problem of the company is price differentiation that used to produce the same product. Kubrom Negash also worked on the same title in Des general trading plc in 2019, the objective of the study is to assess and examine the cost accounting practices utilized by Des General Trading PLC in Ethiopia.

This study adopted a descriptive survey design. The researcher were used both self-administered questionnaire and structured interviews with selected accountants of the finance departments and other department staffs. The major findings of the study are; the most widely 28 used product costing method is process costing and the technique used is absorption costing; the most widely used overhead allocation is units produced; the most important area where the cost information is used for financial accounting, inventory valuation and to some extent for price decisions which is low on other decision making and cost control. Kariyawasam(2018) studied the cost management and account management practices of public quoted manufacturing companies in Sri Lanka.

Research method used in this study was an applied research method, whilst the research strategy employed was a survey research strategy. Sample for the study consisted of 70 public quoted manufacturing companies in Sri Lanka. Findings from the study revealed that the main costing method used by public quoted manufacturing companies in Sri Lanka is activity based costing, followed by process costing and job costing. Findings from the study also revealed that cost information is mainly used by public quoted manufacturing companies for pricing related decisions, followed by customer profitability related decisions, and performance measurement; that the increasing interest and use of cost accounting in these companies is on account of the decline in firm profitability, increasing cost, intense competition, and high customer and supplier bargaining power; and that these manufacturing companies give high importance to traditional management accounting practices such as planning and control, budgeting, target costing, and cost volume-profit analysis. Akeem (2017) the study aimed to examine the effect of cost control and cost reduction techniques in organizational performance.

To examine the issue data were collected from primary source, questionnaires. The data were analyzed by regression analysis to test the hypothesis with the use of SPSS. The researcher was found that cost control has a positive impact on organizational performance. The researcher recommends that cost control and cost reduction scheme must be properly administered in an organization by setting realistic standard. Anand et al (2004) in their study of cost management practices in India studied the responses furnished by 53 CFOs in Indian corporations.

The objective of their study was to capture the development in cost management practices such as accounting for overheads, applications of budgetary control and standard costing in corporate India. The survey questionnaire also aimed to verify any significant difference in management motivation for the implementation and use of standard costing as a control tool between activities based cost management (ABCM) user firms and firms using traditional costing systems.

The study established that the firms are successful in capturing accurate cost and profit information from their ABC cost systems for value chain and supply chain analysis.

The results suggest that the firms have better insight for benchmarking and budgeting with ABC cost system yet the consistency in their priority of budget goals is lacking unlike the firms who are using traditional costing systems. Adebayo et al. (2014) examined the impact of budgetary control on cost control, profitability of manufacturing companies, the causes for deviations and how these variances are reported as a means of control in budgeting and also examined whether the manufacturing companies can reduce cost as well as maintain the quality of their products and services. They used survey method based on 190 staff members Cadbury Nigeria PLC, Friesland Foods Wamco Nigeria PLC and Nestle.

To collect the data primary and secondary source questionnaire was used. The collected data were tested with chi-square statistics through a Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The study discovered that manufacturing companies can reduce cost and maintain high quality products. The study recommended that realistic forecasts should be made and that there should be sound planning with effective and efficient formulation of policies and strategies. Caroline (2014) examined the effects of cost management on the financial performance of manufacturing companies.

The study tried to find the effects of supply chain management, labor management and stock management on the financial performance of manufacturing companies. To conduct the study six manufacturing companies listed on Nairobi Security exchange were selected. The study used quantitative approach as well as casual research design multi variance linear regression model. Data was sourced from both primary and secondary sources namely questionnaire and audited financial statements. The study found that cost management is positively related to financial performance of manufacturing companies.

This research recommended that the management should focus on managing cost of distribution, cost of labor and cost of stock. 30 Even though most of the above studies conducted are mainly discussing studies that are related to the different elements and aspects of cost accounting systems. Some studies also covered cost systems and techniques and others are also related to cost management practices, but there are no in-depth specific study has been conducted covering substantial aspects on the cost management practices related to Ethiopian manufacturing companies on the best knowledge of the researcher; specially in Ok bottling & beverage s.c. previously. The scanning of literatures give an indication that there exists a gap in the existing study and a study is needed that include cost accounting system of Ethiopian manufacturing companies. Thus the main objectives of this paper is examining and evaluating cost management practice of ok bottling & beverage S.C.

The paper also tries to reconcile the different opinions of these studies, contribute some points to the existing knowledge and also will contribute its own share to fill this gap.

Chapter 3-Research Gap

Research Design: Fraenkel, Wallen and Hyun (1993) define research design as the plan by which the researcher answers the research problem. It includes the data collection tools and the data analysis techniques the researcher intends to use. The researcher aimed to resolve the research question by using a descriptive research design which attempts to show the status quo of study items (cooper and schidler, 2006). It is primarily concerned with finding out "what is," in research. It is appropriate when studying relationships and effect of variables on other variables. It studies existing relationships as compared to exploratory research which looks at entirely new relationships. The objective of this study is to assess cost management practices of ok bottling & beverage S.C. Thus, descriptive case study was chosen for this study because it allows the conduct of detailed analysis using multiple sources of data. Case study investigation becomes successful if data is collected from multiple sources (Gerring, 2007).

Research Approach: Descriptive research design involves both quantitative and qualitative data. Quantitative approach involves numerical data subjected quantitative analysis whereas qualitative approach involves data in textual form that concerned with subjective valuation of attitude, thoughts and behavior (Kothari, 2004). 32 According to Schweitzer (2009) quantitative approach was used for its appropriateness to the determination of developing research questions and it is suitable for the type of numerical data required in the study. In this study both qualitative and quantitative data were used. In analyzing case study descriptive research, both qualitative and quantitative research approach is needed (Yin, 2003). That is to get the benefits of a mixed methods approach, and to mitigate the bias in adopting only either quantitative or qualitative approach, the current research combines both quantitative & qualitative research approaches.

Population and Sample Size: The study target population focused on employees of the organization who are working in cost accounting department & other financial departments. Therefore the total employees of the organization working in department of cost accounting, finance & management are 18 and the population for this study that helped to get accurate data was the whole employees. To accomplish the study, the researcher has used a census data collection. This was preferred because it provided the possibility of examining the entire population and acquiring accurate data.

Data Collection Methods: In this study, data were gathered using questionnaires and unstructured interview. Primary data were collected with semi-structured questionnaires distributed to cost accounting department and other financial departments. Structured questionnaires employed to gather straightforward and simple information. Unstructured questionnaire employed to gather information that needs indepth understanding of the topic being studied. However, it may be difficult to classify and measure. Hence, it should be carefully interpreted. 33 Both questionnaires have their own limitations. Dawson (2002) stated that to overcome the limitation of both types, semi-structured questionnaire is preferable and researchers better use the combination of both. In this study, the researcher was used both structured (closed ended) and unstructured (open end) questionnaire. The interview was used to substantiate the data collected using questionnaire, so that the validity of the findings could be improved. The interviews were conducted with respective manager. It is used to cross check the reliability of the response to the questionnaire. Sreejesh, Mohaoatra and Anusree (2014) indicated that depending up on the amount of guidance extended by the interviewer, individual in-depth interviews can be divided in to unstructured interview, structured interview and semi-structured interview. This study employed unstructured interview.

Data Analysis: Data analysis is the application of reasoning to understand the data that have been gathered. In its simplest form, analysis may involve determining consistent patterns and summarizing the relevant details revealed in the investigation. The appropriate analytical technique for data analysis is determined by management’s information requirements, the characteristics of the research design and the nature of the data gathered (Zikmund et. al, 2009). The data collected were analyzed by qualitative and quantitative data analysis methods. The qualitative data analysis was done using content analysis. During this research, qualitative data were collected in the form of description text. According to Bernard (1995, as cited in Armfield S. 2007) “content analysis is a catch-all term covering a variety of techniques for making inference from texts.” Quantitative data analysis was done using descriptive statistical method specifically percentage, frequency distribution and present it with tables in order to avail the finding of the study. Percentages are suitable for comparative analysis of figures. The use of frequency distribution tables by the researcher in analysis of data is to give faster and more understandable presentation of the data collected by the researcher.

Respondents Age

Age	Number of respondents	Respondents in %
Below 25 years	---	---
26-35 Years	10	56%
36-45 Years	6	33%
Above 45 years	2	11%
Total	18	100%

From the above table we can see that 10(56%) of the respondents are within the age of 26-35 years, 6(33%) is within the age 36-45 and the remaining 2(11%) of respondents are above 45 years. In this regard no respondent were the age categories below 25 years. Thus, based on this one can infer that most of the respondents are middle aged. This enhances the reliability of the data collected and the productivity of the organization.

Position in the Organization: Response on department shows 50% of the respondents are in the cost accounting division, the rest 50% are distributed in the other departments; which is 35% Finance, 10% from Top management & the rest 5% from other department. This implies that the respondents working position is not concentrated to a specific post this will positively assist the quality of data collected.

Cost Accounting Practices: Cost Accounting may be defined as “Accounting for costs classification and analysis of expenditure as will enable the total cost of any particular unit of production to be ascertained with reasonable degree of accuracy and at the same time to disclose exactly how such total cost is constituted”. Thus Cost Accounting is classifying, recording an appropriate allocation of expenditure for the determination of the costs of products or services, and for the presentation of suitably arranged data for the purpose of control and guidance of management. Also, Cost Accounting is the process of accounting for cost which begins with recording of income and expenditure and ends with the preparation of statistical data. It establishes budgets and standard costs and actual cost of operations, processes, departments or products and the analysis of variances, profitability and social use of funds.

Thus Cost Accounting is a quantitative method that collects, classifies, summarizes and interprets information for product costing, operation planning and control and decision making. Like any other system of accounting, Cost Accountancy is not an exact science but an art which has developed through theories and accounting practices based on reasoning and commonsense. Many of the theories cannot be proved nor can they be disproved. They grownup in course of time to become conventions and accepted principles of Cost Accounting. These principles are by no means static, they are changing from day to day and what is correct today may not hold true in the circumstances tomorrow.

1. Demand Forecasting-

Many firms are still having trouble anticipating future demand today. The biggest issue is that they lack comprehensive reporting systems that would allow them to forecast how many goods they should sell in the coming months or years. As a result, their products fall short of client expectations, resulting in fewer sales. This is another common problem in the manufacturing industry.

Manufacturers should employ reliable reporting systems that may help them target sales and predict how much and which products they should manufacture in the upcoming term to forecast client demand correctly as these are some common problems in manufacturing industry.

2. Inventory Management & Control-

Inventory management remains one of the most difficult tasks in the manufacturing business, but it has gotten much easier with the help of automated solutions. Nonetheless, many manufacturers, particularly small ones, continue to handle their inventories manually.

Inventory management is a time-consuming task that can be simplified with the use of the software. Manual stock checks are inefficient and prone to errors, which can result in inaccuracies, shortages, and excess, as well as unidentified losses. These very are common problems in manufacturing industry.

3. Efficiency Issues-

Manufacturers have been seeking for efficient solutions to decrease costs and increase efficiency at their operations up until now. Many of them prefer to minimize production costs by sacrificing product quality, but this will only reduce their profitability since disgruntled customers will quit buying from them. These very are common problems in manufacturing industry.

Modernizing processes and systematizing workflows is one of the most effective strategies to increase efficiency in manufacturing operations. Manufacturers must decrease time-consuming and labor-intensive processes, reduce material waste, maximize equipment use by reducing damage, and streamline their supply networks. All of these can be aided by Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) solutions.

3. Issues of Job Costing-

Job costing, cost accounting, manufacturing costs, what does all of this mean? Oftentimes, job costing, cost accounting, and manufacturing costs are used interchangeably. As a manufacturer, it does not matter what you call it. But it is critical that as a manufacturer, it captures all of our conversion costs.

Simply put, we are taking raw material and converting it to a finished good that is ready for sale. You need to capture 100% of those cost of converting the raw material. Most small companies start with the most basic bookkeeping, and that's okay. But there are two huge mistakes manufacturing companies make that you need to avoid.

Eventually, you need to have proper accounting transactions and systems to capture all of those manufacturing costs to have accurate margins. Accurate financial statements and margins will allow you to correctly price your product and will allow you to make adjustments to your business. This is helpful when you have a change in prices of materials or labor, or if your volume throughput changes for whatever reason.

.First, a company may not want to spend the time and money to improve their cost accounting and systems. As a result, this company will struggle forever. The managers of that business will not have accurate financial reports, and they will likely feel the pain when markets turn or are in a high growth situation. Remember, cash gets tight when in either a growth or decline pattern, especially if it's not managed well.

Second, a company wants to improve the manufacturing cost accounting, but they overdo it. They want a report that tracks every penny and part, and they install a massive expensive system. Many times, they install the wrong system for their company because it was marketed as the best accounting system. This happens when companies do not spend the money to go through a system selection process. They all end up spending much more than the cost of the professional system selection and bust their budget.

As a manufacturing company, please consider the following as a best practice for your leadership to abide by.

Chapter 4- Conclusion and Recommendations

The terms Manufacturing Overheads, Factory Overheads, Works Overheads and Production Overheads have the same meaning and are used interchangeably. Manufacturing overheads shall include administration cost relating to production, factory, works or manufacturing and depot. Manufacturing Overheads shall be classified on the basis of behavior as Variable Manufacturing Overheads and Fixed Manufacturing Overheads. Variable Manufacturing Overheads comprise of expenses which vary in proportion to the change in volume of production. For example, cost of utilities etc. Fixed Manufacturing overheads comprise of expenses which does not change with the change in volume of production. For example, salaries, rent, repairs & maintenance, etc.

Material Consumed: Material Consumed includes materials directly identified for production of excisable goods such as:

- (a) Indigenous materials
- (b) Imported materials
- (c) Bought out items
- (d) Self-manufactured items
- (e) Process materials and other items
- (f) Materials received free of cost or at concessional value from the buyer
- (g) Accessories, on which cenvat credit is admissible, and which are cleared along with the final product
- (h) goods used for providing free warranty for excisable good.

Cost of material consumed consists of cost of material, duties and taxes, freight inwards, insurance and other expenditure directly attributable to procurement. Trade discount, rebates and other similar items are deducted for determining the cost of materials. Cenvat credit, credit for Countervailing Customs Duty, Sales Tax set off, VAT, duty draw back and other similar duties subsequently recovered/recoverable by the entity are also deducted. Normal Capacity is the production achieved or achievable on an average over a period or season under normal circumstances taking into account the loss of capacity resulting from planned maintenance.

Packing Material Cost: The cost of material of any nature used for the purpose of packing of excisable good.

Quality Control Cost: The quality control cost is the expenses incurred relating to quality control activities for adhering to quality standard. These expenses include salaries & wages relating to employees engaged in quality control activity and other related expenses.

Repairs & Maintenance Cost: Cost of all activities which have the objective of maintaining or restoring an asset in or to a state in which it can perform its required function at intended capacity and efficiency.

Research and Development Cost: The research and development cost incurred for development and improvement of the process or the excisable good.

Royalty: Royalty is compensation/periodic payments for the use of asset (tangible and/or intangible) to the owner for use of his asset in the production/manufacture, selling and distribution by an entity.

Scrap: Discarded material having some value in few cases and which is usually either disposed of without further treatment (other than reclamation and handling) or reintroduced into the production process.

Principles of Measurement-

- a) Manufacturing cost for each excisable good shall be measured separately.
- b) Manufacturing cost of each excisable good shall be the aggregate of direct and indirect cost relating to manufacturing activity.
- c) Material cost shall be measured separately for each type of material, that is, for indigenous material, imported material, bought out components and process materials, self-manufactured items, accessories for each type of excisable good. Cost of Inputs received free of cost or at concessional value from the buyer of the excisable good shall be considered for determination of manufacturing cost.
- d) The material cost of normal scrap/defectives which are rejects shall be included in the material cost of excisable goods manufactured. The material cost of actual scrap/defectives, not exceeding the normal quantity shall be adjusted in the material cost of good production. Realized or realizable value of scrap or waste shall be deducted for determination of manufacturing cost. Material Cost of abnormal scrap /defectives should not be included in material cost but treated as loss after deducting the realizable value of such scrap / defectives.
- e) Employee Cost for each excisable good shall be measured separately.

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